

A Novel Message Passing Algorithm for Soft-Output Detection in Faster-than-Nyquist Multicarrier Systems

Michele Mirabella*[†], Pasquale Di Viesti*[†], and Giorgio Matteo Vitetta*[†]

**Dept. of Engineering “Enzo Ferrari”, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Modena, Italy*

[†]*Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni (CNIT)*

Email: {michele.mirabella, pasquale.diviesti, giorgio.vitetta}@unimore.it

Abstract—In this manuscript, we focus on the problem of soft-output detection of spectrally efficient frequency division multiplexing in the presence of frequency-selective fading channels. A novel detection algorithm, resulting from a message passing approach to the considered problem and not requiring matrix inversions nor spectral decompositions, is devised. Our approach is based on a novel scheduling criterion applied to the Forney-style factor graph representation of the approximate maximum likelihood detection problem. Our numerical results evidence that the proposed algorithm outperforms, in terms of achievable rates and communication performance, other detectors available in the technical literature at the price of higher computational complexity and sheds new light on the trade-off between spectral efficiency and detection complexity in a communication system employing spectrally efficient frequency division multiplexing.

Index Terms—Detection, Faster-than-Nyquist, Inter-Carrier Interference, Message Passing, Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of *sixth-generation* (6G) of wireless communications, *integrated sensing and communication* (ISAC) has emerged as a key enabler for improving *spectral efficiency* (SE) while unlocking a broad spectrum of sensing applications. A crucial challenge in ISAC is the design of waveforms that allow achieving good performance in both communication and sensing performance under specific spectral and complexity constraints [1]. In this context, one of the available options is represented by *spectrally efficient frequency division multiplexing* (SEFDM) [2], a modulation format closely related to *orthogonal frequency division multiplexing* (OFDM). In fact, similarly to OFDM, the SEFDM format puts into practice the frequency multiplexing concept by employing multiple subcarriers; however, unlike OFDM, it improves SE by giving up the orthogonality constraint, i.e., by increasing the spectral overlap among distinct subcarriers. Unluckily, this advantage is obtained at the price of the introduction of a significant *inter-carrier interference* (ICI) at the *receive* (RX) side and,

consequently, of a higher detection complexity. This has motivated the interest in developing computationally efficient detection and decoding techniques for mitigating the impact of ICI in SEFDM communication systems [3]–[6]. While *maximum likelihood* (ML) detection guarantees optimal communication performance, its computational complexity remains prohibitively high [7]. To address the performance degradation and complexity issues due to the presence of ICI in SEFDM detection, various methods such as *truncated singular value decomposition* (TSVD) and *iterative detection* (ID) have been proposed [3], [5]. However, these methods exhibit relatively poor performance and this makes them impractical for real-world communication systems.

A different approach has been taken into consideration in [8]–[10], where *message passing* (MP)-based detectors for SEFDM under a frequency-selective fading channel have been developed. However, all these manuscripts make use of turbo detection and decoding, a strategy we intentionally avoided in our work since it generally entails a substantially higher computational burden than treating the two tasks separately. Moreover, in [9], the communication performance has been analyzed for a specific SEFDM variant that employs a *time-domain* (TD) *root-raised cosine* (RRC) pulse (being time-limited and, consequently, characterized by an unlimited bandwidth) and does not make use of a *cyclic prefix* (CP) in the modulated signal. Note that, since the RRC pulse shape is not strictly bandlimited, its use entails significant *out-of-band* (OOB) emissions. Moreover, in [9] the problem of compensating for the amplitude distortions due to the non-flat-top spectral characteristics of the RRC pulse has been ignored. From this perspective, the considered modulation format substantially differs from OFDM, which typically makes use of a TD pulse with a flat-top spectrum (e.g., an RRC spectrum) to avoid any form of self-interference in the generation of the multicarrier signal and to assign the same amplitude to all the subcarriers [11, Sec. II-A].

In this manuscript, a novel MP-based detection algorithm for a SEFDM modulation incorporating a CP and sent over a frequency-selective fading channel is illustrated. The remaining part of this manuscript is organized as follows. In Section II, a simple model for the received signal is derived; in doing so, the SEFDM cyclic structure originating from

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the presence of a CP is exploited. Note that the CP plays a fundamental role since it eliminates *inter-symbol interference* (ISI) between adjacent SEFDM symbols, thus reducing the complexity of the receiver. Then, in Section III, a *factor graph* (FG) representing the likelihood function of the considered detection problem is derived and an MP-based algorithm, called *parallel-branch message passing algorithm* (PBMPA), is developed by applying the *belief propagation algorithm* (BPA) [12], together with a specific message scheduling, to the FG itself. The PBMPA generates soft-output information on the transmitted symbols and, consequently, can be used jointly with a soft-input channel decoder. Its performance, when used in combination with a *low-density parity check* (LDPC) decoder, is analyzed in Section IV, where it is also compared with the FSD algorithm [4] and the *Gaussian message passing* (GMP)-based detector described in [9]. Finally, some conclusions are offered in Section V.

Notation: In this paper, the following notation is adopted: 1) $(\cdot)^*$ and $(\cdot)^H$ denote complex conjugate and complex conjugate transpose, respectively; 2) the symbol \odot represents the Hadamard product operator; 3) $R_N[\cdot]$ and $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ indicate the *modulo N* and *floor* operators, respectively; 4) Ξ_V is the unitary DFT matrix of order V , whose element (p, q) is $\exp(-j2\pi pq/V)/\sqrt{V}$; 5) \mathbf{I}_N denotes the identity matrix of order N ; 6) $\mathbf{X} \triangleq [x_{m,n}]$ defines a matrix \mathbf{X} of proper size and $x_{m,n}$ denotes the element appearing on its m th row and n th column; 7) $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the *expectation* operator.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODELS

In this section, we focus on the derivation of a mathematical model for the complex envelope of the transmitted SEFDM signal and of the corresponding received signal in the presence of frequency selective fading. In the following, we assume that: 1) the SEFDM signal conveys the N -dimensional vector $\mathbf{c}_N \triangleq [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{N-1}]^T$, containing N_u channel symbols (which belong to an M_c -ary constellation) and $(N - N_u)$ zeroes; 2) it contains a CP of size N_{cp} ; 3) the modulator *impulse response* (IR) $p(t)$ employed in its generation has an RRC spectrum with *roll-off* parameter α . Our derivation of the SEFDM signal model parallels that provided in [11, Sec. II-A] for an OFDM signal; the main difference is represented by the fact that the vector \mathbf{c}_N undergoes an order N *fractional inverse discrete Fourier transform* (FrIDFT) of positive parameter $\beta \leq 1$ (note that, if $\beta = 1$, SEFDM coincides with OFDM); this produces

$$\mathbf{x}_N = \mathbf{F}_{N,\beta}^H \mathbf{c}_N, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{N,\beta}$ is a square matrix of order N , whose (p, q) th element is equal to $\exp(-j2\pi pq\beta/N)/\sqrt{N}$. Given \mathbf{x}_N (1), a periodic sequence $\{x_k\}$ is obtained by repeating it with period N , so that $x_k = x_{R_N[k]}$ for any $k \notin \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$. Then, this sequence is used to generate the periodic signal

$$s(t; \mathbf{c}_N) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} x_k p(t - kT_s/\beta), \quad (2)$$

where T_s is the *channel symbol interval*. Following the same steps as [11, Sec. II-A], the signal $s(t; \mathbf{c}_N)$ in (2) can be expressed as

$$s(t; \mathbf{c}_N) = \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{NT_s}} \sum_{n=-N_\alpha}^{N_\alpha} X_{R_N[n]} P_{R_N[n]} \exp(j2\pi f_n t). \quad (3)$$

In the last expression, $N_\alpha \triangleq \lfloor N(1-\alpha)/2 \rfloor$ and X_n is the n th element of the vector

$$\mathbf{X}_N \triangleq [X_0, X_1, \dots, X_{N-1}]^T = \Xi_N \mathbf{x}_N, \quad (4)$$

representing the output of the order N *discrete Fourier transform* (DFT) of the sequence $\{x_k\}$ (see (1)). Moreover, in (3), $P_n \triangleq P(f_n)$, $P(f)$ is the *Fourier continuous transform* (FCT) of $p(t)$ and $f_n \triangleq n\Delta_f$ (with $\Delta_f \triangleq \beta/(NT_s)$) represents the frequency of the n th subcarrier.

Let us assume now that $s(t; \mathbf{c}_N)$ (3) is sent over a *frequency-selective* channel characterized by L channel paths, with IR $h(\tau) \triangleq \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} h_l \delta(\tau - \tau_l)$; here, h_l and τ_l denote the gain and the delay associated with the l th channel path, respectively. Then, the useful component of the complex envelope of the received signal after matched filtering can be expressed as

$$r(t; \mathbf{c}_N) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X_n H_n \exp(j2\pi f_n t); \quad (5)$$

here, $H_n \triangleq H(f_n)$ and $H(f)$ is the FCT of $h(\tau)$. In the last expression, it is also assumed that $P_n P_n^* = T_s/\beta$.

Sampling $r(t; \mathbf{c}_N)$ at the instants $t_{\tilde{n}} = \tilde{n}T_s/\beta$ (with $\tilde{n} = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$) and collecting the resulting sequence into a vector produces the N -dimensional vector

$$\mathbf{R}_N = \Xi_N^H (\mathbf{X}_N \odot \mathbf{H}), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \triangleq [H_0, H_1, \dots, H_{N-1}]^T$ is the N -dimensional vector aggregating the complex channel gains.

It is easy to prove that detecting \mathbf{c}_N from \mathbf{R}_N (6) involves first performing an N -point DFT on \mathbf{R}_N , then applying element-wise channel equalization to compensate for the channel \mathbf{H} and, finally, computing an N -point *fractional discrete Fourier transform* (FrDFT) with parameter β . This produces

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}_N \triangleq [\bar{y}_0, \bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_{N-1}]^T = \Psi_{N,\beta} \mathbf{c}_N, \quad (7)$$

where $\Psi_{N,\beta} \triangleq [\Psi_{m,n}] = \mathbf{F}_{N,\beta} \mathbf{F}_{N,\beta}^H$ is the matrix accounting for the intentional ICI. Finally, it is important to point out that the model (7) still holds in the interval $(0, NT_s/\beta)$ if the summation limits $-\infty$ and $+\infty$ appearing in the RHS of (2) are replaced by $-N_{cp}$ and $(N-1)$, respectively.

III. DERIVATION OF THE PROPOSED DETECTOR

In this section, the derivation of the PBMPA is sketched. The devised algorithm is fed by the noisy version of (7), i.e., by

$$\mathbf{y}_N \triangleq \bar{\mathbf{y}}_N + \mathbf{w}_N = \Psi_{N,\beta} \mathbf{c}_N + \mathbf{w}_N, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_N \triangleq [w_0, w_1, \dots, w_{N-1}]^T$ is an N -dimensional complex noise vector¹ having zero mean and autocorrelation matrix

¹It is easy to prove that the elements of \mathbf{w}_N are uncorrelated complex Gaussian random variables having non-uniform variance, provided that the noise, in (7), is uncorrelated and element-wise channel equalization is applied.

$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{w}_N \mathbf{w}_N^H] = 2\sigma_w^2 \mathbf{I}_N$. To begin, we express the conditional probability density function (PDF) of \mathbf{y}_N (8), conditioned on the channel symbol vector \mathbf{c}_N , as

$$f(\mathbf{y}_N | \mathbf{c}_N) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma_w^2} \|\mathbf{y}_N - \mathbf{\Psi}_{N,\beta} \mathbf{c}_N\|^2\right), \quad (9)$$

where \propto denotes the *proportionality symbol*. The last formula can be easily rewritten as

$$f(\mathbf{y}_N | \mathbf{c}_N) \propto \exp\left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_w^2} (2\Re\{\mathbf{c}_N^H \mathbf{\Psi}_{N,\beta}^H \mathbf{y}_N\} - \mathbf{c}_N^H \mathbf{G}_{N,\beta} \mathbf{c}_N)\right), \quad (10)$$

by expanding the ℓ_2 -norm visible in its RHS; here,

$$\mathbf{G}_{N,\beta} \triangleq [G_{m,n}] = \mathbf{\Psi}_{N,\beta}^H \mathbf{\Psi}_{N,\beta} \quad (11)$$

is a $N \times N$ Hermitian matrix. Moreover, the matrix operations appearing in the RHS of (10) can be easily rewritten as

$$\mathbf{c}_N^H \mathbf{\Psi}_{N,\beta}^H \mathbf{y}_N = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i^* \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Psi_{i,j}^* y_j = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i^* z_i(\mathbf{y}_N), \quad (12)$$

with $z_i(\mathbf{y}_N) \triangleq \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \Psi_{i,j}^* y_j$ and

$$\mathbf{c}_N^H \mathbf{G} \mathbf{c}_N = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} G_{i,i} |c_i|^2 + \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j < i} 2\Re\{G_{i,j} c_j c_i^*\}. \quad (13)$$

Note that the last expression has been obtained by exploiting the Hermitian symmetry of the matrix \mathbf{G} , in (11).

Let us now define the functions

$$F_i(\tilde{c}_i, \mathbf{y}_N) \triangleq \exp\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_w^2} \left(\Re\{\tilde{c}_i^* z_i(\mathbf{y}_N)\} - \frac{G_{i,i}}{2} |\tilde{c}_i|^2\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

and

$$I_{i,j}(\tilde{c}_i, \tilde{c}_j) \triangleq \exp(-\Re\{G_{i,j} \tilde{c}_j \tilde{c}_i^*\} / \sigma_w^2), \quad (15)$$

with both \tilde{c}_i and $\tilde{c}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{M_c}$, where \mathcal{S}_{M_c} denotes the set of constellation symbols. Given this couple of functions, (10) can be factorized as

$$f(\mathbf{y}_N | \mathbf{c}_N) \propto \prod_{i=0}^{N-1} F_i(c_i, \mathbf{y}_N) \prod_{j < i} I_{i,j}(c_i, c_j). \quad (16)$$

Based on the last result and on the fact that $P(\mathbf{c}_N) = \prod_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i(c_i)$ (where $P_i(c_i)$ represents the *a-priori probability* of the symbol c_i conveyed by the i th subcarrier), the *a-posteriori probability* (APP) $f(\mathbf{c}_N | \mathbf{y}_N) \propto f(\mathbf{y}_N | \mathbf{c}_N) P(\mathbf{c}_N)$ of \mathbf{c}_N can be expressed as

$$f(\mathbf{c}_N | \mathbf{y}_N) \propto \prod_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i(c_i) F_i(c_i, \mathbf{y}_N) \prod_{j < i} I_{i,j}(c_i, c_j). \quad (17)$$

From the factorization (17), the FG illustrated in Fig. 1 and referring to the i th portion of (17) (with $i = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$) can be inferred. The PBMPA can be derived by systematically applying the BPA (e.g., see [12, App. A]) to this graphical model after a proper scheduling has been established for the exchange of messages among its N portions. In the following, we assume that: 1) all the portions of the PBMPA are fed by the same vector (namely, \mathbf{y}_N (8)), work in parallel and

Fig. 1. Message passing over the portion of FG referring to the i th symbol (with $i = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$). The function block \mathcal{I}_i establishes an interconnection between this portion and the other ones having index $j \neq i$.

Fig. 2. Detailed representation of the custom block \mathcal{I}_i . Note that: a) the dependence of the messages and the function nodes on the variables \tilde{c}_i and \tilde{c}_j are not explicitly shown for simplicity; b) the function $\kappa_i[l] : l \rightarrow \kappa_i[l] \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\} \setminus \{i\}$ is used.

share their statistical information in order to estimate the APPs for the symbol vector \mathbf{c}_N ; 2) the message computation is repeated recursively N_{it} times. The PBMPA is initialized by setting the iteration index n to zero and the input messages $\mathcal{S}_f^{(i)}(\tilde{c}_j) \triangleq \{\tilde{m}_f^{(i,j)}(\tilde{c}_j); j \neq i, \tilde{c}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{M_c}\}$ (with $i = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$) to one. Then, the following steps² are carried out for $n = 1, \dots, N_{\text{it}}$ and $i = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$: **Step 1**) compute the message $\tilde{m}_3(\tilde{c}_i) = \tilde{m}_1(\tilde{c}_i) \tilde{m}_2(\tilde{c}_i) = F_i(\tilde{c}_i, \mathbf{y}_N) P_i(\tilde{c}_i)$; **Step 2**) compute $\tilde{m}_4(\tilde{c}_i)$; **Step 3**) update the set of messages $\mathcal{S}_f^{(i)}(\tilde{c}_i)$; **Step 4**) evaluate the *approximate APP* for the i th symbol as $f(\tilde{c}_i | \mathbf{y}_N) = \tilde{m}_3(\tilde{c}_i) \tilde{m}_4(\tilde{c}_i)$.

The operations executed in **Steps 2)** and **3)** (that represent the core of the proposed PBMPA) are accomplished within the function block \mathcal{I}_i ; moreover, they rely on the operations executed on the *parallel branches* appearing in Fig. 2. Some additional details on this couple of steps are provided below.

Step 2) The function block \mathcal{I}_i is fed by the set of messages $\mathcal{S}_f^{(i)}(\tilde{c}_j)$ originating from the other $(N-1)$ portions of the overall FG and evaluated in the previous (i.e., in the $(n-1)$ th) recursion. Then, the message

$$\tilde{m}_r^{(i,\zeta)}(\tilde{c}_i) = \sum_{\tilde{c}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{M_c}} I_{i,\zeta}(\tilde{c}_i, \tilde{c}_j) \tilde{m}_f^{(i,\zeta)}(\tilde{c}_j) \quad (18)$$

is computed for $\zeta \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\} \setminus \{i\}$. Finally, the message \tilde{m}_4 is easily evaluated as $\tilde{m}_4 = \prod_{\zeta} \tilde{m}_r^{(i,\zeta)}(\tilde{c}_i)$.

Step 3) The messages collected in the set $\mathcal{S}_f^{(i)}(\tilde{c}_i)$ are computed as³ $\tilde{m}_f^{(i,j)}(\tilde{c}_i) = \prod_{\zeta'} \tilde{m}_r^{(i,\zeta')}(\tilde{c}_i)$, for $\zeta' \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1$

²In the following, we will focus our attention only on the operations carried out in the i th portion and in the n th iteration of the PBMPA. Moreover, the iteration index n is dropped from all the messages to ease reading.

³Note that the message computation in **Step 3)** of the PBMPA involves all the branches appearing in the FG shown in Fig. 2 except one (namely, the j th); for this reason, **Step 3)** does not emerge from the direct application of the BPA on that FG.

TABLE I
COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ORDER OF THE CONSIDERED DETECTORS

Detector	FSD	GMP	PBMPA
$\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$	$N_{\text{it}}(N^2 + M_c)$	$N_{\text{it}} N^2 M_c$	$N_{\text{it}}(N M_c^2 + N^2 M_c)$

$1\} \setminus \{i, j\}$.

The output of the PBMPA is the set of APPs computed in **Step 4)** and available at the end of the last (i.e., the N_{it})th recursion.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Extensive computer simulations have been run to assess the performance of the PBMPA and to compare it with that achieved by other algorithms available in the literature; in particular, the FSD algorithm [4] and the GMP-based detector described in [9, Algorithm 1] have been considered. Note, however, that the GMP algorithm was originally intended to operate in a turbo fashion. Conversely, with the aim of minimizing the overall computational complexity, turbo decoding has not been taken into consideration in our work; for this reason, detection and decoding have been treated as separate tasks. This explains why, in the implementation of the GMP algorithm, step 9 in [9, Algorithm 1] has been omitted. Moreover, both the GMP and our PBMPA perform MP in the *logarithmic domain*.

The computational complexity orders $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ of the FSD algorithm, the GMP algorithm and the PBMPA are listed in Table I. From the given formulas, the following conclusions can be easily inferred: 1) the complexity of all the considered detectors exhibits a quadratic dependence on the number of subcarriers N ; 2) the PBMPA has a higher complexity than the other methods and, in particular, its complexity increases linearly with the number of interfering nodes (i.e., N) and quadratically with the constellation size M_c . Note also that the complexity of the GMP algorithm and the PBMPA, being MP-based techniques, can be reduced by omitting the computation of some messages (i.e., those providing a weak contribution in the evaluation of the APPs). With this approach, the complexity can become linear in both the number of subcarriers and the constellation size. However, due to space limitations, this aspect is not further discussed in this manuscript; interested readers are encouraged to refer to [13, Sec. IV-C] for further insights.

Our simulations have aimed at assessing the communication performance achievable on a frequency-selective communication channel when different detection algorithms, operating on a *symbol-by-symbol* basis⁴, are employed at the RX side and their soft output is passed to an LDPC decoder.

In our simulations, the following choices have been made for the transmitted SEFDM signal: 1) number of subcarriers

⁴The detection of SEFDM symbols can be performed in parallel, as the detector processes each symbol independently. Once the soft-output information for all SEFDM symbols is obtained, it must be reorganized into frames to be compatible with the size requirements of the LDPC decoder.

Fig. 3. Pragmatic capacity \mathcal{P}_c achieved by the considered detectors for different number of iterations; $E_b/N_0 = 0$ dB is assumed.

$N = 128$; 2) frequency spacing $\Delta_f = 10$ kHz; 3) CP size $N_{\text{CP}} = N/32$; 4) carrier frequency $f_c = 5$ GHz; 5) roll-off factor $\alpha = 0.15$ for the pulse $p(t)$; 6) compression factor $\beta = 0.8$ (unless differently specified). Moreover, a *quaternary phase-shift keying* (QPSK) constellation has been employed for the information symbols of \mathbf{c}_N . Our choices entail that: 1) the symbol interval is $T_s = 80$ μs ; 2) the cardinality of the constellation is $M_c = 4$. Moreover, an *extended vehicular A* (EVA) channel model has been adopted (this is characterized by $L = 9$ paths) and the availability of ideal *channel state information* (CSI) has been assumed⁵ for channel equalization at the RX side; note that the equalizer accomplishes its task on a *subcarrier-by-subcarrier* basis before detection (e.g., see [14]).

In our simulations, the following performance indices have been assessed: 1) the pragmatic capacity \mathcal{P}_c , i.e., the information theoretical rate achievable through separate detection and decoding [15, Eq. (54)]; 2) the *bit error rate* (BER) achieved by the considered communication system. On the one hand, the first performance metric represents a useful tool to assess the performance of detection alone, independently of the information exchanged with a subsequent decoding stage. For this reason, the pragmatic capacity has been evaluated for different numbers of iterations carried out by each of the considered detectors. On the other hand, when assessing BER performance, the following choices have been made: 1) the number of iterations carried out by all the compared detectors has been set to $N_{\text{it}} = 4$; 2) a binary LDPC code having codeword size equal to 1296 and rate equal to $3/4$ has been employed; 3) an LDPC decoder based on the BPA and accomplishing no more than 10 decoding iterations has been adopted. Moreover, in evaluating both \mathcal{P}_c and BER, the transmission of $2 \cdot 10^6$ information bits has been considered.

Our first numerical results, regarding the achievable rates for the selected detectors, are shown in Fig. 3. In this case, the *signal-to-noise ratio* (SNR) per bit E_b/N_0 has been set to 0 dB and different values for the overall number of iterations have been considered. From these results, it can be easily inferred

⁵Our results show that, despite some performance degradation under imperfect CSI, all the considered algorithms keep working and their performance gaps remain unchanged. These results are not shown due to space limitations.

Fig. 4. Bit error rate performance versus SNR per bit for the considered detectors. The performance achieved by an hard detector in an uncoded OFDM transmission over the same communication channel is also provided as a reference.

Fig. 5. Bit error rate performance versus $\beta \in [0.6, 1]$ for the considered detectors; $E_b/N_0 = 0$ dB is assumed.

that: 1) the PBMPA outperforms the other detectors and almost achieves the maximum symbol capacity (i.e., 2 bit/s/Hz for a QPSK constellation) for $N_{it} \geq 4$; 2) the capacity achieved by the FSD algorithm is maximized for $N_{it} = 4$ and decreases for a higher number of iterations. This is due to the fact that the reduction of the decision radius, being proportional to the iteration index, increases the number of decision errors.

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate some BER results. On the one hand, Fig. 4 shows the BER dependence on the SNR in the interval $[-5, 15]$ dB. In this case, the performance achieved by a hard detector for an uncoded OFDM signal transmitted on the same communication channel is also shown as a reference. On the other hand, in Fig. 5, E_b/N_0 is set to 0 dB and a variable compression factor $\beta \in [0.6, 1]$ is considered, in order to assess the impact of this parameter on error performance.

Based on the results shown in Fig. 4, the following considerations can be made:

1) for $E_b/N_0 < 5$ dB, the GMP detector outperforms the FSD algorithm; however, for higher values of E_b/N_0 , its error performance gets worse. This behavior is due to the fact that the GMP detector is more sensitive to noise variance than the FSD algorithm; this property makes it more appropriate for turbo operations.

2) The PBMPA outperforms the other two techniques and the OFDM detector.

3) The results provided for OFDM refer to the detection of

an uncoded transmission, which requires substantially smaller complexity than that of an SEFDM transmission employing the PBMPA, but achieves a lower SE.

Finally, the results shown in Fig. 5 deserve the following comments: 1) the GMP detector outperforms the FSD algorithm; 2) the error floor of both the GMP and FSD algorithms starts reducing for $\beta > 0.85$; 3) the PBMPA outperforms all the other techniques and, at the given SNR, its floor is not visible in the considered range of compression factors.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this manuscript, a novel MP-based algorithm, dubbed PBMPA, for data detection in a SEFDM-based communication system has been developed. Our simulation results have evidenced it outperforms the other two technical alternatives, in terms of achievable rates and BER performance, at the price of a higher computational effort (which, however, can be potentially reduced through proper optimization). Our ongoing research activities in this field focus on the use of SEFDM for supporting ISAC functionalities.

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